

“A Study To Assess The Effectiveness Of Information Booklet Regarding Janani Shishu Suraksha Karyakram Among The Age Of 20-40 Year Women In Selected Rural Areas Of Jabalpur”

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ABSTRACT: Janani Shishu Suraksha Karyakram (JSSK) launched from Mewat district in Haryana on June 1, unmistakably signals a huge leap forward in the quest to make “health for all” a reality.

METHODS

The study is based on one group pre test and post test design selected by convenience sampling technique. The knowledge regarding Janani Shishu Suraksha karyakram among women collected by using self administered knowledge questionnaire based on JSSK.

SETTING OF THE STUDY “Settings of physical condition in which data collection take place in the study. The settings of study is **SAMPLE AND**

SAMPLE SIZE- Women studying at rural area **Nunsar** Jabalpur

Sample no.-60

MAJOR FINDING OF THE STUDY

- Finding related to demographic characteristics of the sample. • Out of 60 samples most of the sample 34(56.6%), was in the age group 20-25
- Majority of sample 60(100%) female, majority of sample 41(68.3%) were married, Majority of sample 33(55%) were joint families, Majority of sample 35(58.33%) was a rural area, Majority of sample 32(53.3%) was a monthly income
- Finding related to knowledge score before administration of information booklets the result clearly indicated 27(45%) women had poor knowledge regarding information booklets on Janani Shishu Suraksha Karyakram before administration of information booklets on Janani Shishu Suraksha Karyakram 33(55%) had average knowledge.
- Finding related to knowledge score after administration of information booklets on Janani shishu suraksha karyakram. The finding show that 22(36.6%) had good knowledge score and 38(63.3%) had average knowledge score.
- Finding related to comparison of pre test and post test knowledge. The finding mean pre test knowledge score (11.06) the finding mean post test knowledge score (20) is apparently higher than the mean pre test knowledge score.

CONCLUSION

The research result showed significant improvement of the knowledge of women Janani Shishu Suraksha Karyakram among 20-40 year of women information booklets in rural area Nunsar Jabalpur. The effectiveness of planned teaching programme is calculated by t-Test and association between demographic variables and knowledge in calculated by chi-square Test.

Keywords: Janani Shishu Suraksha Karyakram, Pregnant women, Age, Rural, Deliveries

INTRODUCTION

In view of the difficulty being faced by the pregnant woman and partners of sick new -born along – with high out of pocket expenses incurred by them on delivery and treatment of sick – new born, ministry of health and family welfare(MOHFW) has taken a major initiative to evolve a consensus on the part of all states to provide completely free and cashless services to

pregnant women including normal deliveries and caesarean operations and sick new born (up to 30days after birth) in government health institution in both rural and urban area. government of India has launched Janani Shishu Suraksha Karyakram (JSSK) on 1st June 2011.

Janani Shishu Suraksha Karyakram (JSSK) unmistakably signals a huge leap forward in the quest to make “health for all”

a reality. The knowledge about this is important for the mothers

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To assess the pretest knowledge score regarding JSSK among the age 20-40 year women in selected rural areas of the Jabalpur.
- To assess the post test knowledge score regarding JSSK among the age 20-40 year women in selected rural areas of Jabalpur.
- Assess the effectiveness of the information booklet regarding JSSK.
- To associated the pretest and post test knowledge score regarding JSSK among the age 20- 40 year women in selected rural areas of Jabalpur.

HYPOTHESIS

H1: there will be significant difference between pre-test knowledge score and post test knowledge score.

H2:Determine the association of pre test knowledge nursing student regarding janani sishu suraksha kaaryakram.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITION

Structured teaching program - "it is on intervention which guides learning to extent the knowledge of women regarding JSSK". 22

• **Knowledge** – "knowledge refers to correct written responses receiving from women regarding JSSK"

Janani Shishu Suraksha Karyakram-

Launched on June 1, 2011 JSSK is a Government of India entitles all pregnant women delivering in public health institutions to absolutely free and no expense delivery, including caesarean section

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Approach- Quantitative And Evaluative Approach

Research Design- Research Design Is The Overall Plan For Obtaining Answer To The Question .

Pre Experimental One Group Pretest Posttest Design.

Variables

Independent Variable– Information Booklet On Janani Shishu Suraksha Karyakram.

Dependent Variable – In The Study The Dependent Variable Is The Knowledge Of Janani Shishu Suraksha Karyakram.

Setting Of The Study

"The Settings Of Study Is - Rural Area Nunsar

Population Of The Study

Target population-Pregnant women

Assessable population- Women in the age group 20-40 years

Sample and sample size- Women residing at rural area Nunsar Jabalpur

Sample no.- 60

Sampling technique

Purposive sampling technique was used for the study.

Sample selection criteria

Including criteria – Females who are Primigravida

Females who are age between 20-40 years

Females who are willing to participate in the study

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

Females who are already attended and teaching.

Session related to Janani Shishu Suraksha karyakram.

Those who are not present during the time of the study

Those who were not willing to participate in the study.

DESCRIPTION OF THE TOOL

The structured questionnaire constructed by the investigation consist of two sections.

•Section A —SOCIO DEMOGRAPHIC The section consist of age type of family monthly income occupation of family head previous knowledge.

•Section B – QUESTIONNAIRE Questionnaire for assessing the knowledge regarding JSSK. This section consist 30 questions. Each correct answer fetched one Mark. The areas of question divided into three group. Incidence and knowledge.

CRITERIA MEASURE

Knowledge score – 30

The maximum score – 30

Minimum score – 0

Scoring is categorised as Level of knowledge

Score

Good 21-30

Average 11-20

Poor 0-10

ANALYSIS OF DATA

Analysis as the categorizing, ordering manipulation and summarizing of the data to reduce it to tangible and interpretable forms. So that research problem can be studied and tested including the relationship between variable. 39 The analysis of data was done in accordance with the objectives of the study. The data was analyzed by calculating percentage, mean percentage, standard deviation and 't' value.

SECTION-1 :- Sample characteristics of data collection study.

SECTION-2 :- Relationship of Janani Shishu Suraksha karyakram knowledge with the selected demographic variable of the total subject i.e. age Marital status.type of family, occupation of husband of family, previous Knowledge about Janani Shishu Suraksha karyakram.

No of sample: - 60

No of question asked :- 30 Criteria of validation of sample: - '1' marks for each correct answer and "0" Mark for each wrong answer.

Section 3 : Data on effectiveness of health education regarding the effect Janani Shishu Suraksha karyakram.

Section 4 : Data on association between the Post test level of knowledge and the selected demographic variable among Janani Shishu Suraksha karyakram.

SECTION-1

DEMOGRAPHIC DISTUBATION OF AGE GROUP

The indicate that 34 (56.6%) of woman belongs to 20-25 years of age group and 21(35%) or woman belongs to25-30 years of age group 2(3.3%) of woman belongs to 30- 35 years of age group 3(5%) of women belongs to 35-40 years of age group

DEMOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION OF MARITAL

Indicate that 41(68.3%) of woman are married and 0% are unmarried and 13(21.6%) woman are widows and 6(10%) woman are divorcee.

DEMOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION OF OCCUPATION OF HUSBAND

Indicate that 30(50%) mans are farmer and 6(10%) mans are in private job and 23(38.33%) mans are in other job and 10(1.6%)are in govt. job .

DEMOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION OF TOTAL MONTHLY INCOME

The table no. 4 indicate that 32(53.3%) total monthly income is <10,000 and 15(25%) are total monthly income is 10,000-15,000 and 4(6.6%) are total monthly income is 9(15%)are total monthly income is >20,000

DEMOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION OF TYPE OF FAMILY

Indicate that 33(55%) woman belongs to type of joint family and 27(45%) of woman are belongs to nuclear family.

DEMOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION OF PREVIOUS KNOWLEDGE REGARDING JSSK

Indicate that 28(46.66%) of woman gain knowledge from mass media and 10(16.66%) of woman are gain knowledge from reading books and 14(23.33%) of women gain knowledge from parents and sibling and 8(13.3%) gain knowledge from neighborhood

DEMOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION OF EDUCATION

INDICATE THAT 13(21.6) WOMEN EDUCATION ARE PRIVATE AND 23(43.3%) WOMEN EDUCATION ARE PRIMARY AND 21(35%) WOMAN EDUCATION ARE HIGHER SECONDARY AND 0(0%) WOMEN EDUCATION ARE GRADUATE.

SECTION-2 PRETEST KNOWLEDGE OF WOMEN AGE GROUP 20-30 YEAR REGARDING JSSK ASSESSMENT
N=60

S.NO.	CATEGORIES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE	MEAN	SD
1.	GOOD	0	0		
2.	AVERAGE	33	55	11.067	3.53
3.	POOR	27	45		

The data presented in table no.9 fulfill the objective : 1 clearly indicate that 0(0%) women have good knowledge and 33(55%) women have average knowledge and 27(45%) women have poor knowledge about JSSK .The mean & SD also justify the knowledge of women.

SECTION-3 POSTTEST KNOWLEDGE OF WOMEN AGE GROUP 20-30 YEAR REGARDING JSSK ASSESSMENT

S. NO.	DISCRIPTION	MEAN	SD
1	POSTEST	20	3.03

SECTION -4

It deals with the comparison of pretest and post test knowledge score of women effect of health. TABLE NO. 9 Comparison of pre test and post knowledge score and health education of women age group 20-40 year of age about JSSK

S. NO.	DISCRIPTION	MEAN	SD	't' VALUE
1	PRETEST	11.06	3.53	4.33
2	POSTEST	20	3.03	

Table no. 9 fulfill the table no. 9the comparison of pre and post knowledge made by correlation is the appropriate statistical method of to compare the pre and posttest knowledge score the result showed position correlation

SECTION -5 ASSOCIATION AGE- NS, Marital status- NS, Occupation of husband- NS, Monthly income-NS, Previous knowledge- NS, Education- NS

ETHICAL GUIDELINES- -

- permission heading CHC & PHC
- Consent for pregnant women
- Building Trust in women
- Protecting participant safety

NURSING IMPLEMENTATION

The finding of the study has implication for nursing practice, nursing administration, nursing education, nursing research, and public education.

NURSING PRACTICE -Finding of the study indicate lack of knowledge in community women's.It implied that an implementation of booklet assisted structured teaching programme to community women's would increase the level of knowledge about JSSK

NURSING EDUCATION -It stimulates the interest of participants to carry out the research and involved themselves in research activity.there should be adequate guidance, supervision and evaluation of community women's regarding and their knowledge about JSSK.

NURSING ADMINISTRATION- With increase awareness women's the nursing administration have a responsibility to prove a substantive opportunity with the help of information

booklet regarding JSSK. This will enable women's to update their knowledge about JSSK

RECOMMENDATION -

- On the basis of the study may be replicated on a large sample so that the finding can be generated
- The study may be replicated on a large sample in a community setting.
- The study may be conducted in nunsar, jabalpur.

LIMITATION1. Women from selected rural area of jabalpur.

2.The size of the sample is only 60.

3.The is conducted to the women's who have under the 20-40 year of age.

CONCLUSION

The research study concludes that study supports the need for the community and the women's living in the community. In this study booklet assisted structured teaching programme was effective to increase the knowledge regarding the jananishishusurakshakaryakram among 20-40years of women's So, the aim of the research study is to assess and provide knowledge regarding janani shishu Suraksha karyakram with the effective booklets among the age group 20-40year of women in selected rural area Nunsar, jabalpur.

In this study information booklet was independence variable and knowledge was dependence variable. **Good (36.3%)**

Average (63.3%)

Poor (0%)

It is concluded that booklet assisted structured teaching programme was effectiveness the association finding was done to find out the relationship of knowledge with selected demographic variables

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